

CORRECTIONS CAREERS

EUROPEAN CAREER COUNSELLING GUIDELINES
FOR STAFF WORKING
IN CRIMINAL CORRECTIONAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

WP2

**2.3 STRUCTURED
PUBLIC HEARING**

PT

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CAREERS

***Gathering
intelligence about
the future of CCI
Careers***

IPS_Innovative Prison Systems

March, 2021

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Introduction to Portuguese Context

Education: In Portugal, when applying for the prison officer's competition, candidates must have high school education completed (at least), have Portuguese nationality, have 21 years old and have no criminal record. Candidates undertake several tests and evaluations to enter the Prison Officers Initial Training Course, namely: physical and theoretical knowledge tests, medical examinations and Psychological assessments (Decree-Law no. 3/2014, article 36^o)¹.

Training: In Portugal, the initial Training provided to prison officers has a nine-months duration: six months of Training comprising theoretical and practical contents on penal and prison legislation, human rights, English, communication, interaction with inmates, ICT, security, video surveillance and telecommunications, personal defence, health, communicable diseases and first aid, psychopathology, criminology, criminal profiling, among others; and three months Training comprising the real work context component, allowing trainees to contact with the requirements and demands of the job and the application of knowledge to specific situations for solving problems, within the scope of professional activity (Ordinance n^o. 159/2017)².

Prison officer status: There are two careers within the scope of Prison Officers legislation; one incorporates management functions/roles, and the other a more operational dimension. With public security functions, prison officers are arranged in a hierarchical order. This division and the definition of the functional contents of the different categories are essential for the Prison Officer to respond more adequately and effectively to the requirements of the current prison system. The prison officers with public security functions are grouped in a descending hierarchy order. (Decree-law no. 3/2014)³.

¹ Decree-Law no. 3/2014. Accessible here: <https://dre.pt/pesquisa/-/search/571052/details/maximized>

² Ordinance n^o159/2017. Accessible here: <https://dre.pt/pesquisa/-/search/108016472/details/maximized>

³ Decree-law n^o3/2014. Accessible here: <https://dre.pt/pesquisa/-/search/571052/details/maximized>

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Overview of career guidance policy developments: The Portuguese Legislation foresees that one unit is responsible for Training and professional development within the Portuguese Prison and Probation Services: The Directorate of Human Resources. This Directorate encompasses three divisions: 1) Human Resources Management Division; 2) Personnel Administration and Remuneration Processing Division; 3) Training Division. The Human Resources Management Division, among other duties, is responsible for promoting, monitorisation and implementing performance evaluation systems and preparing internal training contents. On the other hand, the Training Division is responsible: for the identification of the training needs and professional improvement; to propose and implement human resources development policies concerning initial and continuing Training, namely those resulting from activity plans or change processes; to define and assess the of training methodologies and professional development actions on staff's productivity and services provided, also promoting the use of alternative training methods (e.g., e-learning); to disseminate training actions and to ensure the procedures related to registration, attendance control and certification; to prepare the annual training activity report, among others (Order no. 8140-B/2019⁴). This training plan is developed biannually and distributes Training in nine main areas⁵:

- **Area 1: Execution of Sentences and custodial measures** – within this first area, Training is more focused on penitentiary legislation and inmate's processes management (aiming a better systematisation of procedures within this area);
- **Area 2: Execution of Sentences and Alternative Measures and Electronic Monitoring** – within this second area, Training aims to enhance the case management model followed by The Portuguese Prison and Probation Services, based on the RNR principles, LS/CMI and Motivational Interview. Concerning electronic monitoring teams, Training focuses on communication skills and relationship management with the offender to prevent conflict and the escalation of violence;
- **Area 3: Execution of punitive-educational measures**, where Training focuses on three essential aspects: the need to update both on the regulations of the

⁴ Order no. 8140-B/2019. Accessible here: <https://dre.pt/home/-/dre/124716436/details/maximized>

⁵ Retrieved from The Portuguese Prison and Probation Services 2018-2019 Training Plan. Accesible here: <https://dre.pt/application/conteudo/124716436>

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Educational Centres; the used assessment tools and the promotion of the general improvement and consistency of technical intervention;

- **Area 4: Security and prison behaviour** – where Training focuses on tackling the prison officer's training needs;
- **Area 5: Prison Treatment, Rehabilitation, Health and Programmes** – where Training focuses on the qualification of deputies and senior technical staff on penitentiary treatment, the application of risk assessment tools and methodologies in prison settings;
- **Area 6: Criminology and Law** – where Training focuses on the promotion of a training offer with an academic profile, with two main objectives: 1) to tackle the needs of developing and updating knowledge in the legal and criminological fields; 2) to disseminate and to promote the exchange of knowledge and experiences resulting from their academic or research path;
- **Area 7: Administration and Management of Human and Financial Resources** – where Training focuses on public administration, staff management, public employment, and HR/personnel development;
- **Area 8: ITC and Communication Systems** – where Training focuses on tackling the needs regarding the user's automation of information;
- **Area 9: Initial Training and Admission** – Training focuses on two brief courses for new Probation Officers and an Initial training course for prison officers.

Furthermore, a mandatory performance evaluation (i.e. self-assessment and hetero-assessment) occurs for the following categories: 1) public services, 2) public administration directors, and 3) public administration workers, by using the Integrated Management and Performance Evaluation System in Public Administration (SIADAP)⁶. This evaluation system encompasses three subsystems that are

⁶ Law n°66-B/2007. Accessible here: <https://dre.pt/web/guest/legislacao-consolidada/-/lc/34446375/view?w=2012-12-31>

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directly related to the abovementioned categories. Thus, every year, SIADAP 1 is applied to evaluate the performance of public services. SIADAP 2 aims to assess the public administration directors' performance and is applied every three or five years (five years for senior managers and three years for middle managers) according to the service commission's duration. Lastly, SIADAP 3, which is the one most relevant for our research object, is applied to public administration workers every two years (concerning the performance of the two preceding years) and encompasses the following elements: 1) academic and professional qualifications; 2) Professional experience; 3) Curricular valorisation; 4) Performance of managerial positions/coordination or other positions or functions or recognised public interest or relevant social interest (Law nº 66-B/2007)⁷. According to the article 52º of the Law, nº 66-B/2007 this performance assessment aims the following: 1) to identify the worker's personal and professional skills that need development, 2) to perform a training needs diagnosis, 3) to identify the professional competencies, skills and behaviours that need improvement; 4) to improve the workplace and associated processes; 5) to revise the worker's adjustments regarding career progression and salary positioning, and to assign performance bonuses, under the terms of the applicable legislation. Thus, and based on article 54º of the aforementioned Law, this performance evaluation system should identify the worker's potential for evolution and development and the diagnosis of the respective training needs that should be considered in each service's annual training plan.

According to the Law nº 66-B/2007, the SIADAP (and its subsystems) articulates with the Ministry's planning system, being an evaluation tool for each Directorate multi-annual strategic objectives, annual objectives, activity plans and training plan. Despite the annual development of objectives and plans for each Directorate, and as mentioned before, the correspondent assessment, in terms of periodicity, varies from SIADAP 1, SIADAP 2 and SIADAP 3. However, this preconised assessment is not focused on the correspondent current year but in the preceding years.

⁷ Law nº 66-B/2007. Accessible here: <https://dre.pt/pesquisa/-/search/227271/details/normal?q=Lei+n.%C2%BA%2066-B%2F2007%2C%20de+28+de+dezembro>

Report from Portuguese Survey

Participants

There was a total of 118 participants, including 90,68% prison officers ($n=107$), and 9,32% probation officers ($n=10$). Figure 1 indicates the years of work of the participant's current positions.

Figure 1. Years of work in the current position

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Results

For most participants, 64,41% (n=76), this is the only career they had, with 71 participants (60,17%) mentioning not being satisfied with the work. Also, and in line with the expressed, 96, 52% of the participants (n=111) considers that their salary is not fair (pondering the type, the time and intensity of work that needs to be done). We can see that in the barometer in figure 2.

Figure 2. Is your salary consistent with your duties? (n=111)

The participants present high demotivation levels when performing their roles and jobs, as shown in figure 3.

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Figure 3. Motivation to perform duties

In accumulation with high levels of demotivation and wage satisfaction, the participants mentioned three main reasons prison officers quit their jobs; they are: lack of professional development; low income; and lack of training, followed by work in shifts, and insufficient vacations.

The 3 main reasons to quit the job are (n=105):

Figure 4. Main reasons prison officer quit (n=105)

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When asked about their job's risk, the prison officers mentioned various risks. We decided to group them in terms of context and significance (figure 5): physical health/burnout; security risks, Attacks/Aggression; Lack of Staff; Bad leadership.

Figure 5. The most frequently mentioned main risks are (n=105)

Alongside this data, most participants think that their work does not provide enough training and education to perform the tasks and job (figure 6).

Figure 6. My organisation provides me with a good education and professional competences to perform my job (n=105).

And for this reason, career training is almost non-existent, with annual reviews that don't translate into practical activities. There is no mentorship in the professional environment to help the professional deal and cope with the difficulties encountered when performing the job. We can see this information on a visual level in figure 7, with a barometer of achievement and the number of participants who refer to the existence of those conditions.

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Figure 7. Visual barometer

Nonetheless, all the constraints, the participants consider their job a public role (with a mission to ensure society's safety) and a profession (like any other). Still, they do not consider their job a career, where they can progress and be stable professionally (figure 8).

Figure 8. When I go to work, I consider it to be (n=105)

Conclusion

This survey's objective was to gather information about the future of CCJ careers and why/how guidance is needed and necessary to be set in place.

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We were able to gather information on policy and strategy's critical issues are being considered for career guidance in CCJ careers (what a favourable and an unfavourable outcome is). The future workshops designed to be delivered this month (February) will shed light on the key operational, structural, and cultural challenges that need to be made to deliver the expected outcome.

From this survey, we were able to identify the significant difficulties in assessing training and education to perform the tasks and job, and the problem in a proactive leadership between professionals, to better fulfil the job ahead of them.

We were also able to identify the need to manage a career in the learning prison context, mental awareness (when the participants mentioned stress, security issues and burnout), and difficulty communicating and dialogue in the multicultural context.

We were able to identify the inexistence of a tool for self-assessment of competencies, leading to a personal development planning tool.

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Next steps

For this purpose, the public structure hearings (in the form of 2-hour workshops) will be highly relevant.

Suppose we want to compare how certain types of people talk about CCJ careers. In that case, we must separate them into different groups (guards and technical staff, probation officers, and research specialists in this field). That way, we can analyse across the correctional officers' group, the probation officer that work directly with the prisons and /or community and the research specialists, and then compare the findings. If we mix them in the same group, it would be more difficult to analyse based on experience on the subject.

We are dividing the groups based on characteristics to create a more comfortable environment for participants to share. Strengthen the 'information harvesting' results in WP2 to give us even more robust data to base the rest of our project. It will underline the input's importance to enhance the outcomes, especially the quality of careers for prison staff and their support. The questions to be discussed in the online meeting have been prepared with the questionnaires' results and the country reports (national policy context) in mind.

For this purpose, we are in the phase of conducting a Structured Public Hearing, to look for the range of opinions, perceptions, ideas, or feelings that people have about career guidance in CCJ careers. We understand that may differ in groups' perspectives (in this case, different correctional criminal justice professionals – guards and technical staff, probation officers and research specialists in this field). People in decision-making positions may see a situation or issue differently than those who are not, and top management often sees issues differently than frontline providers.

Develop a profile of competencies (complex cartography of skills, behaviours, and attitudes) needed to support career management, interactive tool to help users navigate the profile, self-assess, obtain development solutions, and support personalised learning pathways to strengthen the competencies.

There will be held **three groups according to the participants' previous distributions**. Each group will last, at a **maximum of 2 hours**. This time definition concerns the participants' involvement, who can

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participate in a short workshop and provide input to the project, at the expense of more extended participation in which they could not attend. Also, the pandemic context that we live in does not allow a presential workshop, so the meeting will be held virtually through one platform (to be decided according to the participants' availability).

Preparation Activities

In the stage of preparation for the workshop, the project team from IPS_Innovative prison Systems established the list with potential participants to the meeting and send them an invitation for collaboration with a short description of the project "European Career Counselling Guidelines for Staff Working in Criminal Correctional Justice System" on **the 12th of February of 2021**, to attend a virtual zoom meeting in *the 4th of March 2021*.

The project team analysed the preliminary questionnaires' results, and the *PowerPoint* presentation was prepared to be presented to the workshop.

To conduct the workshop, the hosting organisation team prepared and sent on 19/02/2021 the invitation with a short description of the project's agenda. Something so that participants know what to expect. The project's introduction, what this activity is, and what we will do with this discussion results.

Because the workshop was planned in an online format, the time was more limited, and the communication had to consider the particularities of digital communication. Considering these aspects and improving the channels of communication and data collection, we asked to record the session.

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Workshop brief description

Taking into consideration the pandemic context that we live in, the workshop was organised in an online format using the **platform Zoom, with three different meeting links and hours, from 09h00-11h00 (academic experts), from 14h00-16h00, (unions and Governmental organisations); from 16h00-18h00 (probation professionals (prison staff, and community probationers).**

The workshop's objective was gathering national intelligence about the future of CCJ careers and why/how guidance is needed and necessary to be set in place.

The workshop was focused on seven broad areas:

- The critical issues for the policy and strategy area being considered for career guidance in CCJ.
- What a favourable outcome is.
- What an unfavourable outcome is.
- Critical operational, structural, and cultural changes need to be made to deliver a favourable outcome.
- Lessons from the past.
- Decisions that must be prioritised.
- What the participant would do if (s)he had absolute authority.

The workshop was attended by 4 participants (one academic, one from Union, and two correctional staff).

Main discussions

The moderator **Ângela Fernandes** (set some ground rules; warm-up; introductory questions; guided questions, etc.), concluding the workshop's question and conclusion.

Conclusions and proposals

After the 4th of March, when the project team captured ideas from the workshop discussion and received the participants answers to the question list, the outcome was centralised and presented in the next table.

Questions	Outcomes of this discussion and according to written answers of participants.		
	<i>Academics</i>	<i>Union/Governmental Institutions</i>	<i>Probationers and prison staff</i>
<p>Is your salary consistent with your duties?</p>	<p>Area of investigation: development of career and vocational career, in prisoners.</p> <p>It implies understanding the context of work: a demanding and generally qualified job.</p> <p>Workers' dissatisfaction with work conditions in general about lack of staff, what is reflected in wage compensation.</p> <p>If they (the government) are unable to improve the work environment, unless they need to improve their salary and make it match the tasks.</p>	<p>At the end of 2019, professional social reinsertion technicians, senior social reinsertion technicians and senior re-educations technicians, integrated in the different Organic Units of the DGRSP, performed their duties.</p> <p>These technicians perform functions of paramount importance, critical to the maintenance of Constitutional order through the prevention of crime and social integration of adults and young offenders or those at risk of crime,</p>	<p>The salary is always the same since I joined.</p> <p>If they really pay me for the work, I do I'd also say that they don't.</p> <p>I practice a position with responsibility and in comparison, with other functions I do not earn differently.</p> <p>Fair wages in a pandemic situation would be different.</p> <p>I do not consider that it is entirely underpaid, even if some salary is supplemented by Extras, which is what leads me to</p>

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		<p>functions that are of special complexity and demand.</p> <p>And their salary has not been updated ever since.</p>	<p>answer that I do not agree with the bad salary.</p> <p>In fact, in relation to what is required of the prison guard corps it is not underpaid.</p> <p>I think it reflects lacks progression of careers that is a bit of an echo of the successive crises that the country is going through.</p>
<p>I avoid telling people I work in prisons?</p>	<p>Engaging in the sense that it may be more intense than what it mirrors.</p> <p>A matter of more than Prejudice of protection, personnel security, and to avoid the pressure of peers and others.</p>	<p>Often, the professional does not wish to say where he works for safety reasons or in other cases, he intends without Prejudice to say what his profession is.</p>	<p>In an open establishment and with visibility to the outside, there is no problem saying that I work in a prison establishment because we are also an example for the outside and are well regarded.</p> <p>I believe that there are some who cannot have a good image and who can take the refusal to say that they work in a</p>

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			<p>prison.</p> <p>I was never ashamed of the profession, but I know that there is an associated stigma.</p> <p>I confess that at the beginning they showed some surprise for being a female and young prison guard When I entered.</p> <p>In my day-to-day life I try and if I am in uniform to send a message of professionalism and age so that I and people lose the stigma associated with prison guards.</p> <p>It is unfortunate that there are people with this shame And with this stigma to describe and saying their roles.</p>
<p>When I go to work, I consider it to be...</p>	<p>Is it a job—a profession with specificity, like many other jobs that enter the social domain (security forces).</p>	<p>They provide technical advice to courts with a high degree of qualification and responsibility in risk</p>	<p>It is difficult to answer at this point, but I consider it a profession.</p>

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	<p>Considering what is behind, who are underpaid, who protect themselves by not saying what they do, but after 75% consider it a profession and a mission, I think it is a positive fact.</p> <p>75% do not have a negative representation of their work, at this level, but this conflicts with all other aspects and this is what is interesting, trying to understand why.</p>	<p>assessment, reintegrating offenders, and monitoring the execution of custodial sentences and measures to detain youths in educational centres.</p> <p>For this reason, the technicians consider their work a mission and give themselves to him, body, and soul, which is not reflected in the policies designed.</p> <p>This may imply that in the future there may be a high disengagement with its mission and that there will be a proliferation of corruption.</p>	<p>Now, the situation is very complicated, and we have a lot to do, a lot of sacrifice, to take the goals Forward.</p> <p>The lack of staff and it turns out to be very difficult for the people who retired and there is no one to replace them.</p> <p>Given this I consider a profession and a mission that we must fulfil and carry to the end.</p> <p>Competing for the career as such, I did not know at all what they did and how they did it.</p> <p>One of the interviews in the selection spoke about the life of the prisoner, and he believed that this career could help people to</p>
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			<p>rehabilitate themselves.</p> <p>I confess that I do not see it as a mission. It is very individualised. It is a career. But there is no prospect of it. There was a contest 15 years ago, never again.</p> <p>Even though the legislation points to a correctional service, the Portuguese context is still very penitentiary.</p> <p>Perhaps the mission would be achieved if there were the resources (of social, human, and economic structure).</p>
<p>I think that my organisation provides me with a good education and professional competences to perform my job?</p>	<p>There is no training. Was it important to know how many Training they had during their career time and on what topics?</p> <p>Often Training is carried out without any meaning that is not reflected in the trainees' functions and</p>	<p>For this reason, there is a need to create a body of employees who master the technical knowledge, experience, and training necessary to pursue the ends assigned functionally in the framework of the staff performing</p>	<p>We are not given the tools, and the demands are made without the resources to do so.</p> <p>There is no training. Or access to Training.</p>

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	needs.	functions in the Directorate-General for Social Reintegration and Prison Services.	<p>I must take time off on vacation to be able to get Training.</p> <p>There are annual training maps (for prison guards and administrative staff) that later for various reasons (lack of means, resources, ect) end up not being completed. And when they are disseminated, they reach a reduced target population for those who are in need.</p> <p>Since 2007, where I am working, I have participated in 3 training actions, it is very few in face of the reality of numbers that we have.</p> <p>The professional entity does not help with Training. All the Training I did was out of service, but the service benefits from the</p>
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			<p>same Training, because I have the credentials for that, and the entity applied for financing with my credentials.</p> <p>Lack of will. Fear that people will evolve in the system. There is no good training in this regard.</p>
<p>Career guidance in basic Training.</p>	<p>What is career counselling, in the first place, for them? The concept is dubious, and the answer can be influenced, as none of this is career counselling. This is the preparation to take place.</p> <p>Unfortunately, in Portugal, Career advice is called a lot that is not really career advice.</p> <p>Career counselling for the job market process can be one of the points to address.</p> <p>Despite calling in Career counselling This is not what they are doing.</p> <p>What confirms the care in the elaboration of</p>	<p>However, the respective professional career has not been revised to date, nor regulated as a remarkable career in the scope of Public Administration, although the need for this regulation stems from the Law and has been repeatedly recognised by the Ministry of Justice, being not only a claim of these professionals, as a necessity due to their specificity.</p> <p>SinDGRSP understands that it is of the most elementary justice that the legislative proposal for the</p>	<p>I do not believe there is any career advice at all. The focus was on Training to end as quickly as possible to work, acquire knowledge (such as decorating and debiting), and move on to the next one.</p> <p>Focus on the final classification and there is no career guidance.</p> <p>As a probationer, I had informal Training, and I had a probationer who supported me, and I was always accompanied with him,</p>

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	<p>the questionnaire and in the questions that are asked.</p> <p>There is a lot of confusion in career counselling. And career counselling is confused with career development, with professional placement which are different things.</p> <p>I think that here we talk more about career development. When I talk about this confusion in international terms, there is also this misunderstanding.</p>	<p>creation of the unique career of reinsertion technician of the General Directorate of Reinsertion and Prison Services (DGRSP).</p>	<p>informal mentoring. It was not something designed and structured by the entity.</p>
<p>I have an annual review.</p>	<p>The annual evaluation is essential, but what they gain from it, often in the public service, nothing is gained from it, as it does not allow them to move up the ladder of progress in their careers.</p> <p>Evaluation Does not add anything</p>	<p>Annual assessment is carried out; the requirements are defined; however, there is no impact on the evolutionary career of the professional who works.</p>	<p>The evaluation is partial; it depends on who evaluates,</p> <p>It is very unfair.</p> <p>There are limits on grades, but it must be done, and you have to try to reward those who work, which does not always happen, so it is not always fair.</p> <p>The question of</p>

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			the annual evaluation has always been a battle for everyone (even before touching people's pockets - the level of money) because it does not reflect later on in the career progression and depends a lot on who the supervisor is, who does it and if I get along with him or not, regardless of the criteria being established.
I have a mentor.	It is essential, and only 13 mentioned having a mentor.	There is no formal mentor person. What exists is informal mentoring for the introduction to your task or your job.	Informal mentoring, or none.
The most frequently mentioned risks are:	Interesting risks mentioned. This result is entertaining and can also help to explain everything else. Aggression Security is all interconnected. We could make a gigantic Cluster.	They travel to the places where electronic surveillance is carried out, in cases of confinement in the home and removal of victims, being the first line of intervention in crisis situations, ensuring the monitoring and psychosocial	Rearranging the order of the risks: Lack of staff and poor leadership. Lack of staff reflected in safety and physical health / burnout.

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	<p>All these risks It translates because they consider they job a mission. And all the dissatisfaction around it and how it can be balanced?</p> <p>Poor leadership has very big implications for their career development and career management. For me it is also an expression of career dissatisfaction and those responsible for it.</p> <p>Do not feel protected by the leaders.</p> <p>It is interesting to see these studies being complemented by more qualitative studies. This can be explained by the answers they gave in avoiding saying that I work in social reintegration/prison guard, as they are interconnected. And also, for the associated stigma.</p>	<p>monitoring of the guarded. It is important to highlight the permanent availability for the provision of work at any time and on any day, whenever requested, and the special risk inherent to the nature of the activities and tasks concretely committed.</p>	<p>It would change the order (it would be security, attacks and aggressions first, and then the others) that then lead to situations of burnout.</p>
<p>The three main reasons to quit the job. Are:</p>	<p>It reinforces everything that was said above:</p> <p>Difficult working conditions, poorly paid, and lack of Training reinforce everything</p>	<p>Lack of Career Recognition Lack of Career Prospects cause internal mobility to be too high for each service and for each</p>	<p>I agree with the three of them, and if I left, I pointed out the lack of staff. I feel alone at work and there are no</p>

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	<p>that has been said above and once again reflects the absence of a new and implemented career development, to produce effects.</p> <p>The problem is in working conditions and lack of prospects.</p> <p>Perhaps they feel abandoned. The feeling I have of these data in general is that they feel abandoned.</p> <p>People feel little support: they are not recognised in career development: which is different from career management. There are no prospects for career development, underpaid and no care with Training and education.</p> <p>Abandonment by supervisors.</p>	<p>profession.</p> <p>In addition, this internal mobility is often dubious. Although the Law is clear.</p> <p>What makes the professional who wishes to change careers have between them and the position they want to acquire a lot of obstacles.</p> <p>They feel abandoned by the legislator at the time of the merger. That until today has not solved his situation or legislation on his job, Despite the constant requests and the constant struggles in cited by Unions.</p>	<p>conditions, the lack of career prospects in terms of probationers leads me nowhere.</p> <p>100% lack of career perspective, since 2002, I never had the chance to apply for a leadership course because when opened one back in 2005 I still didn't have enough time to apply and they haven't opened it since then.</p> <p>There is no career prospect.</p>
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Workshop Evaluation

For the workshop's evaluation, the Innovative Prison System project team prepared an online survey and invited all participants to answer. The questions were:

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You want to add something?

Thank you for your participation and involvement.

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Communication

The workshop was in Portuguese Language.

During the event, the member from Innovative Prison Systems project team **Ângela Fernandes** presented the next power point materials:

Pictures of the workshops

The screenshot displays a presentation slide with the following content:

- Top Left:** A gauge chart titled "O seu salário é correspondente às suas funções? (n=115)". The needle points to "Sim" (Yes), with a count of (n=111).
- Top Right:** A gauge chart titled "Evito dizer que trabalho em prisões/reinserção social (n=105)". The needle points to "Não" (No), with a count of (n=62).
- Bottom Left:** A pie chart titled "Considero o meu trabalho: (n=105)". The data is as follows:

Category	Percentage
Profissão	37,14%
Uma missão	38,10%
Outro	12,38%
Uma carreira	12,38%
- Right Side:** Logos for "CORRECTIONS CAREERS" and "INNOVATIVE PRISON SYSTEMS". Below the logos is the text "Resultados dos questionários de PORTUGAL." and two small video thumbnails.
- Bottom:** A video player interface with a progress bar and control icons.

CORRECTIONS CAREERS

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Resultados dos questionários de PORTUGAL.

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Annexes

Annexe 1 Agenda

- Introduction of the facilitators (5 minutes)
- Introduction of the project (5 minutes)
- Presentation of the data and discussion (50 minutes)
- Questions and conclusions (5 minutes)

Annexe 2 – list of participants

Ask to put the name and organisation in the chat: we took a print screen and there are the registry of presences.

Paulo Cardoso – Universty of Évora- School of Sciences

Mário Melo Barroso – Union - Sindicato dos técnicos da Direcção-Geral de Reinserção e Serviços Prisionais

António Padrão- Técnico Superior- estabelecimento Prisional de Izeda Bragança Correctional facility

Lina Caetano – Guarda prisional – Santa cruz do Bispo-feminino- correccional facility.
Peace missio in South Sudan

CORRECTIONS CAREERS

Annexe 3-Presentation

CORRECTIONS CAREERS

**EUROPEAN CAREER COUNSELLING GUIDELINES
FOR STAFF WORKING
IN CRIMINAL CORRECTIONAL JUSTICE SYSTEM**

CPIE **SNPP** **York Associates** **Freie Hansestadt Bremen** **BETI** **IPS** **CEIPES** **ICPA**

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CORRECTIONS CAREERS

Objetivos do Projeto

- *Corrections Careers* é um projeto financiado pela União Europeia, que analisa a forma como podemos melhorar a orientação de carreira dada aos profissionais que trabalham na linha da frente das prisões e os técnicos de reinserção social.
- O projeto está a decorrer nas prisões de seis Estados-membros Europeus. Perguntamos aos agentes prisionais, técnicos de reinserção social, aos seus gestores, e a decisores o que poderíamos fazer para apoiar melhor as suas carreiras no sistema prisional.

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Resultados dos questionários de PORTUGAL.

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O seu salário é correspondente às suas funções? (n=115)

Evito dizer que trabalho em prisões/reinserção social (n=105)

Considero o meu trabalho: (n=105)

Resultados dos questionários de PORTUGAL.

O seu salário é correspondente às suas funções? (n=115)

Evito dizer que trabalho em prisões/reinserção social (n=105)

Considero o meu trabalho: (n=105)

Considero que a minha organização providencia educação e formação profissional para melhor exercer a minha atividade (n=105).

Resultados dos questionários de PORTUGAL.

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Resultados dos questionários de PORTUGAL.

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CORRECTIONS CAREERS

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Questions List

The questions were the same as the questionnaire, and we only asked them to elaborate on them to better understand the reasoning behind their answers.

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